

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ALEMAYEHU****FIRST NAME: HEWAN****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 01****INSTRUCTOR: Dr GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Essay Writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Paraphrasing (EUCLID 2019, 8)
3. Style Guide (EUCLID 2019, 24)
4. Simple writing (EUCLID 2019, 15)
5. The Opposing View (EUCLID 2019, 14)

COURSEPACK REVIEW

1) INTRODUCTION

The first period of ACA-401D focused on academic writing and the requirements to achieve this writing level at Euclid University. Cleenewerck & Gulma's coursepack begins with a step-by-step process of how best to write an academic essay. It states that "an academic essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence" (EUCLID 2019, 6). The coursepack discusses plagiarism, emphasizing how to cite the work of others in one's essay. The literature review section included mostly reminders such as the use of proper punctuation and to use the active voice unless there was a need for passive. There is a segment on style guide, and the American vs. British English, and the importance of picking one and using it throughout. The following chapters included sample corrections to papers, highlighting what appeared to be common mistakes, CMS crib sheets and Latin abbreviations and expressions.

The study material also included a video narrated by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck detailing how to use the word template, properly cite references, and a tutorial on how to convert to and from US or UK English in Microsoft word.

2) ESSAY WRITING

The first chapter of the coursepack addresses academic essay writing. Cleenewerck & Gulma go into great detail to explain what this entails: understanding the question asked, researching the topic, planning and using the relevant information, and finally, writing the essay. Furthermore, a thorough explanation of the essay structure, including a breakdown of the type of information to include in the Introduction, Body, and Conclusion, is addressed. The chapter ends with information on referencing and ideas to consider while editing the essay (EUCLID 2019, 1-4). I believe this is an essential part of the course because it lays the foundation for writing academic essays, in this program. There are several students with different academic backgrounds in this program. Drawing from my experience alone, having worked as a healthcare provider, the last time I had written an essay was in graduate school 12 years ago. I think that including a process such as this one is beneficial to the student because it streamlines the workflow.

3) PARAPHRASING

The topic of plagiarism is addressed a couple of times in the coursepack. There is a clear definition, and examples. I think a student must have a thorough understanding of this subject matter, even though there is technology that can scan a document and show that level of plagiarism. I found the information on paraphrasing especially helpful because it shed light on a topic, I find a little confusing. Cleenewerck & Gulma provide a concise definition and further explain that when paraphrasing, you must use your own words, the writing style must be different, there must be an "accurate representation" of the author's ideas, and the work must be cited (EUCLID 2019, 7). Although this is a matter addressed at all levels of one's education, I think it is especially vital at the Doctorate level due to the copious amount of reading and writing involved.

4) STYLE GUIDE

Cleenewerck & Gulma explain the concept of style guides by first talking about the recommendation at Euclid University and then stating that it "is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent" (EUCLID 2019, 23). I believe it is important to have consistency in your writing style, making it easier for the reader to follow the author's idea and not get distracted. It seems the style guide acts as a framework. This concept plays on another notion the authors bring up, with regard to writing. It is to write clearly, sentences should be short and easy to understand that "your writing should focus readers' attention on the ideas you wish to express, not on the words you have chosen to express those ideas" (EUCLID 2019, 14). The concept appears to be simple enough, but it sounds important enough to have made it into the coursepack, giving the impression that the authors felt a need to address it.

5) THE OPPOSING VIEW

Another concept I found interesting is the idea of putting yourself on the other side of a discussion and trying to understand where that person is coming from regarding their view. Philosophers have done their research and taken their time to write papers and books, and so are basing their point of view on the outcome of all the work they have put into it (EUCLID 2019, 14-15). It is often easy to argue a side without truly understanding the other point of view or even what they are basing their ideas on. As I continue my studies, I hope to implement this concept to further understand why the author holds the view he/she does.

6) CONCLUSION

This is my first assignment in this Doctoral program. I had anticipated the first few assignments to be especially difficult since it involves acquainting oneself with new methods and preparing for what is ahead. It took some time to look through all the information to figure out exactly how to get started. Looking back, I think that the information was all there, but there might have been some anxiety concerning the material amount. The coursepack for period one is well assembled. I felt much of the information I knew but had not thought about or used in a long time, so it was great to have a refresher. Also, it appears Cleenewerck & Gulma might have put this coursepack together as a quick reference for assignments moving forward, so I can see myself using the material throughout the program.

The video tutorial narrated by Prof. Cleenewerck was helpful in setting up the template for the response paper. I am a visual learner so being able to see the setup instead of reading instructions and following along made for a smooth set up.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent." Basic ACA 401 Tutorial." Vimeo Video 2016.
<https://vimeo.com/157480457>

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.